

GENETIC DIVERSITY ANALYSIS OF DIFFERENT GENOTYPES OF SOYBEAN (*Glycine max* L. Merr.) BY USING SSR MARKERS.

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Abstract

In the present study, 34 SSR primers were screened which successfully discriminated the soybean genotypes. The screened primers were able to generate 68 amplicons with an average two amplicons per primer and out of total amplicons, 57 amplicons were found polymorphic. They showed 83 per cent polymorphism and the average number of polymorphic bands per primer was 80% different primers produced a different level of polymorphism among the different genotypes.

The similarity coefficient among all varieties ranged from 0.33 to 0.87. In present study polymorphic SSR could clear the distinguish varieties. Dendrograms were generated based on data recorded by the one marker systems. The result of cluster analysis indicated the separation of different varieties within same species. JS-335 and IVT CODE 22 showed least similarity of 0.33% and IVT CODE 25 and IVT CODE 37 shows highest similarity i.e. 0.87.

Key words: soybean, SSR markers, Cluster analysis,

Introduction

Soybean is an important oilseed crop of the world. It is the premier oilseed crop in India occupying more than 12 million hectare under cultivation; however, its average productivity (~1.0 t/ha) is far below the world average (~2.5 t/ha). The escalating demand for soy-based food products due to an increased awareness about its health benefits and multifarious applications is asking for enhanced production and productivity of soybean. Soybean in India which was introduced during 1963 from the USA (Agarwal *et al.* 2013) maintains a narrow base gene pool (Delannay *et al.* 1983; Gizlice *et al.* 1994). Further, the wild-type germplasm which constitute an underutilized hidden reservoir of useful genes (Wang *et al.* 1992; Lark *et al.* 1995; Maughan *et al.* 1996; Mian *et al.* 1996; Orf *et al.* 1999a, b) has been least used in soybean genetic studies and breeding programmes in India (Yashpal *et al.* 2015).

The estimation of genetic diversity between different genotypes is important in plant breeding programmes and also essential for constituting linkage map. Genetic diversity can be studied by using morphological markers are preferred as they are based on the genotypes of an individual, show genetic variation on a more detailed level and are free from the environmental effects/factors.

Several molecular marker techniques are available for detecting differences within and among genotypes. For example, Random Amplified Polymorphic DNA (RAPD), Inter-Simple Sequence Repeat (ISSR), Simple Sequence Repeat (SSR), Single Nucleotide Polymorphism (SNP) and Isozymes.

Materials and Methods**Plant material**

32 genotypes of Soybean (*Glycine max*(L.) Merr.) Were collected from MPKV, Agricultural Research Station, Digraj, Sangali, Maharashtra and used as experimental material

List of Selected Soybean Genotypes.

Sr.No.	Name of Genotype	Sr.No.	Name of Genotype
1	IVT CODE-21	17	IVT CODE-34
2	IVT CODE-22	18	IVT CODE -35
3	IVT CODE-23	19	IVT CODE -36
4	IVT CODE-24	20	IVT CODE-37
5	IVT CODE-25	21	IVT CODE-01
6	IVT CODE-26	22	IVT CODE-02
7	IVT CODE-27	23	IVT CODE-11
8	IVT CODE-28	24	IVT CODE-12
9	IVT CODE-30	25	IVT CODE-13
10	IVT CODE-06	26	IVT CODE-14
11	VT CODE-09	27	IVT CODE-16
12	VT CODE-10	28	IVT CODE-17
13	VT CODE-29	29	IVT CODE-18
14	VT CODE-31	30	AMC 100-39
15	VT CODE-32	31	NRC 147
16	VT CODE -33	32	IVT CODE 20

Morphological Characters

Plant Height at Harvesting.
Days to Flowering from Sowing.
Days to Physiological Maturity from Sowing.
Number of Pods per Plant.
Seed Number per Pod.

Test Weight.**Seed Yield.**

The seeds of each soybean were grown on college field to study different morphological characters.

Observations recorded:

Data were recorded on seven quantitative characters of thirty two selected soybean varieties.

Quantitative Descriptors:

Plant height at harvesting (cm): Height measured from the base of the plant to the tip of the main shoot at harvesting stage.

Days to flowering from sowing: Days to flowering is the first flowering at reproductive stage and measured from the day of sowing.

Days to Physiological maturity: It is the growth stage that is measured from days from sowing in which plant has mature pod color which can be brown, golden, yellow or gray depending on Genotypes

Number of seeds per pod: Number of seeds in randomly selected pods at harvesting stage.

Test weight (g): Weight of hundred well dried seeds selected randomly from intermediate portion of the plant.

Number of Pods per plant: Number of pods per plant at harvesting stage.

Seed Yield Per Plant (g): Weight of all well dried seeds from individual plant.

Table 3.2: Components of 2% extraction buffer.

Sr.No.	Components	Quantity
1	10% CTAB	20 ml
2	4 M NaCl	35 ml
3	1 M TrisHCl (pH 8)	10 ml
4	0.5 M EDTA	4 ml
5	0.2% β -mercapto ethanol	400 μ l
6	0.3% PVP	500 μ l
7	Sterile distilled water	31 l

Chloroform-isoamyl alcohol mixture was prepared in the ratio of 24:1 (v/v) Working quantity.

RNase treatment:

1 μ l of RNase was added into the 100 μ l of isolated DNA and incubated at 37°C for 1 hour in hot water bath to remove RNA contamination.

Agarose Gel Electrophoresis:

After RNase treatment DNA band were separated by agarose gel electrophoresis.

Dilution of DNA samples

A part of DNA sample was diluted with appropriate quantity of TE buffer to yield a working concentration of 30 ng/ μ l and stored at 4°C

The components, stock and volume of PCR reaction mixture (15 μ l):

Sr. No.	PCR Reaction Components	Final Concentration	Volume for one tube (μ l)
1.	2X PCR master mix (<i>Taq</i> DNA polymerase, dNTPs, MgCl ₂ and reaction buffer)	2X Master mix (High-Media)	7.5
2.	F Primer	5-25 Pmol	1
	R Primer		1
3.	Distilled water	-	5.5
4.	Template DNA	10-60ng/ μ l	1
5.	Total volume		15

Temperature Profile for PCR Amplification:

Sr. No.	Steps	Temperature (°C)	Duration (min)	Number of cycles
1	Initial Denaturation	94	10	1
2	Denaturation	94	1	35
3	Annealing	50-59°(depends on primer)	1	
4	Extension	72	1	
5	Final Extension	72	10	1
6	Hold	4		

Resolution of amplified PCR product:

After PCR amplification, the PCR products were separated by Agarose gel electrophoresis. The amplified products were resolved on 1.5% agarose gel at 50V for 2 hours. The gel was stained with ethidium bromide (0.5 μ g/ml). After electrophoresis, the gel was carefully taken out of the casting tray and photograph was taken on a UV transilluminator.

Data analysis:

NAAS Rating – 04.17

Plantation of Soybean genotypes

The seeds of soybean genotypes were obtained from MPKV, Agricultural Research Station, Digraj, and Sangali. Seeds were sown on agriculture field for morphological observation.

They were allowed to grow with regular irrigation of once a week up till appropriate growth essential for morphological observation and DNA isolation was obtained. Three weeks young leaf tissue was used for DNA extraction.

Methodology

Growing of seedlings

The clean and round seeds of each genotype were germinated in germination paper and general precautions were taken for germination of soybean. Young fresh leaves (10-15 days old) of soybean were used for DNA extraction.

Isolation of Genomic DNA

The plant genomic DNA was extracted using Cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB) protocol.

2% Extraction buffer

for further work until PCR amplification. (By using formula $N1V1=N2V2$).

PCR Analysis of DNA samples

Optimization of PCR Conditions

The PCR amplification for SSR analysis was performed according (Williams *et al.* 1990) to with certain modifications. The optimum specifications followed for DNA amplifications were as follows. SSR primers were used for the PCR amplification.

The SSR fragments scored after diversity database analysis and were recorded as 1 (band/ peak present) and (0 band/peak absent). Molecular weight of the bands was estimated by using 100 bp DNA ladder as standards. All amplifications were repeated at least twice and only reproducible bands were considered for analysis. Percent polymorphism was calculated by using the formula
Number of polymorphic bands

Per cent polymorphism = $\times 100$

Total number of bands

Similarity between the genotypes was generated in the form of binary matrix, based on Jaccard's similarity coefficient.

Genetic similarity estimate (Jaccard's coefficient) based on SSR banding patterns used for cluster analysis to present genetic relationships in the form of dendrogram.

Dendrogram generated using the program NTSYS-pc (version 2.02) developed by Rohlf (1990).

Extraction of genomic DNA and quantification

Results

DNA was extracted using modified CTAB method described by Saghai-Marooof, (1984) with some modification. The 0.8% agarose gel electrophoresis showed good quality of DNA. The quantity of DNA was checked by using 1 μ l of DNA of each 32 genotypes by using Bio-Spectrometer (Eppendorf). Quantity of all samples was found to be in the range of 66.8-875.4ng/ μ l. These samples were diluted to a final concentration of 10-60 ng/ μ l working samples by using TE buffer. The SSR primers were used to amplify genomic DNA and amplified product was resolved on 3.5% agarose gel by staining with ethidium bromide.

DNA image

Figure.4.1:-Genomic DNA of 32 Genotypes on 0.8% agarose gel

Table 4.4: Result of DNA quantification

Sr.No.	Variety	Concentration of DNA (ng/ μ l)	OD (260/280nm)
1.	IVT CODE-21	182.3	1.8
2.	IVT CODE-22	493.6	1.8
3.	IVT CODE-23	104.2	1.81
4.	IVT CODE-24	580.1	1.79
5.	IVT CODE-25	118.6	2.0
6.	IVT CODE-26	456.7	1.8
7.	IVT CODE-27	52.7	1.77
8.	IVT CODE-28	275.6	1.9
9.	IVT CODE-30	167.3	1.9
10.	IVT CODE-06	120.5	1.79
11.	VT CODE-09	146.9	1.81
12.	VT CODE-10	875.4	1.76
13.	VT CODE-29	302.7	1.90
14.	VT CODE-31	97.0	1.96
15.	VT CODE-32	385.6	1.80
16.	VT CODE -33	227.8	1.83
17.	VT CODE-34	374.4	1.80
18.	VT CODE -35	66.8	1.74
19.	VT CODE -36	81.6	1.78
20.	VT CODE-37	151.4	1.80
21.	IVT CODE-01	470.5	1.8
22.	VT CODE-02	401.3	1.8
23.	VT CODE-11	350.5	1.75
24.	VT CODE-12	367.8	1.71
25.	VT CODE-13	244.1	1.74
26.	VT CODE-14	232.0	1.79
27.	VT CODE-16	367.5	1.89

28	VT CODE-17	300.9	1.73
29	VT CODE-18	110.7	1.72
30	AMC 100-39	180.1	1.8
31	NRC 147	470.5	1.8
32	IVT CODE 20	401.3	1.75

PCR amplification by SSR markers

Figure 4.3.PCR Amplification of 32 Genotypes by using Primer Satt 174 on 3.5 % Agarose gel.

Figure 4.4.PCR Amplification of 32 Genotypes by using Primer Satt 251 on 3.5 % Agarose gel

34 SSR primers were screened which successfully discriminated the soybean genotypes. The screened primers were able to generate 68 amplicons with an average two amplicons per primer (Table no.4.5).

Out of total amplicons, 57 amplicons were found polymorphic. They showed 83 per cent polymorphism and the average number of polymorphic bands per primer was 80% (Table 4.5). Different primers produced a different level of polymorphism among the different genotypes.

Table 4.5. List of SSR primers and polymorphic amplicons generated.

Sr.No.	Primer code	Total no of amplicons	Total no of polymorphic amplicons	Percent polymorphism
1	Satt-174	02	1	50
2	Satt-251	03	2	66
3	Satt-367	02	1	50
4	Satt-409	02	1	50
5	Satt-538	03	2	66
6	Satt-236	02	1	50
7	Satt-545	03	2	66

Discussion based on published research paper Chauhan *et.al.*,2015 used 21 SSR markers on 48 genotypes the values lied between 0.1-0.4 with average of 0.267, indicating an considerable diversity among the genotypes Maximum GS0.72 was found between the genotypes MAUS81 and MAUS71; while minimum GS 0.05 was observed between the genotypes MAUS2 and PK262.

In the present study, genetic diversity among *Cicer species* was analysed by 36 SSR primers among 32 varieties. The similarity coefficient among all varieties ranged from 0.33 to 0.87. In present study polymorphic SSR could clear the distinguish varieties.

Dendrograms were generated based on data recorded by the one marker systems. The result of cluster analysis indicated the separation of different varieties within same species. JS-335 and IVT CODE 22 showed least similarity of 0.33% and IVT CODE 25 and IVT CODE 37 shows highest similarity i.e. 0.87.

Cluster Analysis:-

FigNo.37:-Dendrogram showing results of SSR analysis of Soybean genotypes:-

Summary and conclusion

In present study, the similarity coefficient value ranged from 0.33 to 0.87 across 32 genotypes indicating high degree of genetic variation. This ultimately means high range of genetic diversity among the genotypes studied. The highest genetic similarity to an extent of 0.87 was recorded between IVT CODE 25 and IVT CODE 37 genotypes. Least genetic similarity 0.33 was observed in between JS-335 and IVT CODE 22.

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